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Change

All I see is change.
It feels like we're opponents
I'm a melee, you're a range.
You're no longer the one whom I've been
with in those moments.

We've been friends - almost the 'best';
The way you act now brings burden on my chest.
We're no longer alike;
To reach you now is like taking a mountain hike.

The old times you always come near,
we're almost siblings, irresistibly.
Now, we're no longer together;
Seeming like another fake 'forever'.

The best times were outweighed,
all good things fade.
Nothing more to hide;
All those and a height of pride.

I don't know which is right:
To let myself lose you now or to still fight?
The risk I'll always take
is to gain the old you for our friendship's sake.

If I could only initiate a remake,
even just a single retake;
Then those unnerving changes in the arrays,
will no longer pass through our days.